

The Meaning of Cynism in the Novel Bayang Suram Pelangi by Arafat Nur

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Abstract:- The language style in the novel describes the characteristics of an area, the condition of society, and the situation that occurs. Language style shows the direction and intent of a person when expressing words, both orally and in writing. This research deals with the style of language in the novel Bayang Suram Pelangi by Arafat Nur. This study aims to describe the meanings of cynicism in Arafat Nur novel Bayang Suram Pelangi. The reason for this research is to find out what meanings are contained in the novel Bayang Suram Pelangi by Arafat Nur. The research type is qualitative and descriptive type. The research data is in the form of the meaning of cynicism and the source of research data on the events in the Bayang Suram Pelangi Novel. Data collection was carried out by reading and noting events containing cynicism. Analysis of the research data uses content analysis techniques by uncovering, understanding, and capturing messages in the novel. The results of research on the meaning of cynicism in the novel Bayang Suram Pelangi by Arafat Nur, there are (1) nine contextual meanings, (2) nine data conceptual meanings, (3) three data connotative meanings, (4) two data collocative meanings, (5) six data affective meaning, (6) four data social meaning, (7) one data thematic meaning.

Keywords:- The meaning of cynicism, novel.

I. INTRODUCTION

Language style depends on the speaker and who the interlocutor. Style of language can show a person character, the situation of a place, and regional background. Language style is a form of rhetoric, besides that language style is also related to situations that create certain moods. that language style is also related to situations that cause certain moods. For example the impression of good, bad, and happy (Lubis in Hasanah et al., 2019; Muzayanah, 2020).

Sentences on an event in a novel sometimes cross the boundaries of its usual meaning or deviate from its literal meaning so that the readers interpretation does not match the author intent (Pradopo, 2009). (Halimah & Hilaliyah, 2019) concludes several expert opinions regarding the notion of language style (Aminuddin, 2019) Language style is an interesting element in a reading. The presence of language style has become a necessity, as a tool to influence book readers. (Lafamane, 2020) concluded that figurative language

is often referred to as a figure of speech, which is a way of choosing language that suits the taste of the author.

One type of language style is cynicism, which is a style of language in the form of satire in the form of mockery of one's sincerity. Cynicism is a type of anomie, where anomie will lead someone to rebellion whose process consists of 3 elements, (1) vague feelings of hatred, envy and hostility, (2) feelings of helplessness, and (3), experiencing both feelings continuously repeatedly (Dayakisni, 2015; Hasanah et al., 2019). Cynicism can be interpreted as satire containing ridicule which can evoke the emotions of the interlocutor. Cynicism is considered more violent than irony, but sometimes it is still difficult to distinguish between the two. In this case, the function of the cynicism style makes the interlocutor aware. Cynicism is a style of language that aims to satirize something roughly (Kurnianti, 2020; Kusumawati, 2010; Mara & Bahry, 2019; Urahmah, 2017).

Meaning in sentences can be studied as a linguistic phenomenon itself, not as something outside language (Clarencia, 2018). Boundaries regarding the understanding of meaning are difficult to determine because language users have different abilities and perspectives in interpreting an utterance or word (Muzaiyanah, 2015). The grouping of types of meaning is done based on the needs of analysis in a study. Leech (in Wahyudin, 2019) classifies the types of meaning, namely lexical meaning, grammatical meaning, referential meaning, non-referential meaning, denotative meaning, connotative meaning, contextual meaning, collocative meaning, affective meaning, social meaning, and thematic meaning. The use of language style can also be used to clarify or sharpen the meaning in a work so that the message the poet wants to convey to the reader can be more easily accepted and understood (Hasanah et al., 2019).

The meaning becomes part of the world that provides an explanation or meaning of the word. Cynicism can be interpreted as a satire with a pattern of doubt, containing ridicule of sincerity and integrity. Cynicism is derived from the name of a school of Greek philosophy which originally taught that virtue is the only good, and its essence lies in self-control and freedom. But then they become harsh critics of social customs and other philosophies (Heru, 2018; Riemer, 2010; Waridah, 2017).

This research deals with the style of cynicism contained in Arafat Nur's novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*. Arafat Nur's novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* was published by Diva Press in 2018. The novel consists of 384 pages. The *Bayang Suram Pelangi* novel is a literary work that tells the turmoil of the war that occurred in Aceh in the past. This novel has the theme of history and education which tells the story of the character Saidul, a teenage boy who was studying during the war. Cynical language, rudeness, mutual distrust, mutual suspicion, and even violence are commonplace.

The novel is a literary work of the author imagination. The author offers a situation or conflict that is adapted to the reality of a person's life, both life conflicts experienced by the author himself and conflicts experienced by other people (Hasniyati, 2018; Susilowati, 2016). Novels have meanings, elements and values that can be fully understood, only by understanding the function of the entire contents of the novel (Abdulfatah et al., 2018; Sari & Budiawan, 2013). The novel is a part of the written language whose development is inseparable from the creativity of the author. One of the manifestations of the author creativity is through language style (Ibrahim, 2015; Rosyida et al., 2021). The aesthetic nature of this novel can be seen in how the author presents the characters with the problems they face through the use of symbols (Sugiarti, 2019).

Research related to novel analysis and language style has been done before, namely research conducted by (Jannah, 2021) analyzing forms of violence against children in the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* by Arafat Nur, the forms of violence, namely physical violence carried out by hitting and kicking, psychological violence that causes fear, worry, helplessness, and lack of confidence, verbal violence that is done using harsh words, insults, and threats, social violence that is done by exclusion.

Furthermore, the research conducted (Nurmawar, 2020) analyzed human rights violations in Arafat Nur's novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*. The research suggested that the ways of conveying human rights violations that were found were the two types of delivery methods, namely direct delivery methods and indirect delivery methods. The most widely used mode of delivery in the novel is the indirect mode of delivery. There are only a few ways of direct delivery.

(Susilowati, 2016) Language Style in the *Pesantren Impian Novel* by Asma Nadia, this study suggests the types of language styles contained therein, namely (1) comparative and contradictory language styles; (2) Comparative language style in the form of simile, metaphor, personification, allegory, antithesis, pleonasm and tautology, periphrasis, and correction, (3) Opposition language style, namely hyperbole, litotes, innuendo, paradox, climax, cynicism, and sarcasm, (4) metaphorical language style (5) paradoxical language style.

The research conducted (Herman et al., 2018) analyzed the Irony Style in Thayerb Loh Angen's Novel *Teuntra Atom*. The research shows that the style of irony contained in the novel *Teuntra Atom* by Thayerb Loh Angen includes meiosis, cynicism, innuendo, antifriction, sarcasm, satire, and irony.

Furthermore, research conducted by (Cahyo et al., 2020) analyzed the use of sarcasm in Jason Ranti's *Communist Danger Song*. The results of his research show that changes in meaning in the type of rudeness occur due to the wrong choice of words in the song. The sarcasm that arises from the lyrics of the communist danger song not only damages the aesthetics of the song but also ethics which can have an impact on the interpretation and character of the audience.

Based on previous research, it can be stated that this research focuses on the meaning of cynicism in the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* by Arafat Nur. Previous research did not examine the smallest subject in the novel in the language style section. It can be found from the results of previous research, the researcher analyzed the novel completely, while in this research the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* was carried out by paraphrasing the novel, the researcher revealed the meaning of cynicism based on the events that had been arranged in the events table.

The purpose of this study is to describe the meaning of the cynicism style contained in Arafat Nur's novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*. This is interesting because it is seen from the background of the novel that is shown based on the civil war that occurred in Aceh. From this, researchers and readers can understand the influence of war on the everyday language used by the people. Assumptions put forward by researchers because literary works can be created based on facts that happened in the past or individual stories.

Assumptions or basic ideas really need to be formulated clearly before starting to collect data. The need for researchers to formulate basic assumptions or assumptions is (1) Literature always involves setting in developing a story, namely linking the conditions of the time setting in the story and the language or figure of speech used. (2) Representation of the author's views in the past in improving or animating a story related to literature. (3) A demand from nature or geographical location is very decisive in making fictional works that involve creatures around them to bring a story to life. Thus, it is hoped that the writer can describe the meaning and use of cynicism and sarcasm in the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* by Arafat Nur.

This research can be a reference for further studies related to language style, especially the meaning of cynicism. Many research has been done on the style of language contained in novels, but there are not many things related to the meaning of cynicism in novels set in war. War-themed novels usually contain research related to elements of violence, the reality that occurs in the novel.

II. METHOD

The research conducted falls into the category of descriptive research. This research tries to describe something systematically and carefully regarding actual facts, explaining it with a telling pattern. The purpose of this research is to reveal the meaning and use of cynicism and sarcasm in Arafat Nur's novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*. In this study the authors used a qualitative approach, research data was expressed in verbal form and analysis without using statistical techniques. Research with this method uses natural

settings and hides phenomena that occur and is carried out in ways that involve various existing methods (Moleong, 2010).

The data category in this study is text that has been paraphrased into a novel of events that describes the style of cynicism, namely meaning. Qualitative research was carried out in order to be able to describe facts related to an image in a descriptive form, namely the dictions of the research subjects (Ratna in Wibisono et al., 2018). The data source for this research is the event table in the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* by Arafat Nur.

The data collection technique used in this study is the technique of reading and writing which contains meaning, the use of cynicism and sarcasm in Arafat Nur's novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*. Data analysis is the process of searching and systematically compiling data obtained from the results of data collection. The data analysis technique used in this research is content analysis technique. Content analysis

A. Results

Table 1: Contextual Meaning

No	Occurrence Number	occurrence	Page
1	5	<i>Kampung yang membuat orang lain menderita</i>	13-16
2	14	<i>Jin-jin peliharaan tidak dapat membantu mereka</i>	16-38
3	16	<i>Penggeledahan rumah Pasha Alibasyah</i>	38-39
4	17	<i>Pasha Alibasyah tidak bisa membaca</i>	38-39
5	22	<i>Saidul berbincang dengan tentara</i>	39-43
6	30	<i>Kucing menyembul dari balik pagar</i>	43-61
7	37	<i>Anak-anak tidak peduli dengan pendidikan</i>	61-102
8	40	<i>Saidul terdiam</i>	102-106
9	56	<i>Tentara jarang mau memuji</i>	106-216

The table above is data showing contextual meaning in Arafat Nur's novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*. The context itself is a situation that is formed because there are settings, activities and relationships. If there is interaction between the three components, a context is formed. It will be difficult to understand the meaning of a discourse if we ourselves do not understand the context in which the utterances occur. To understand an utterance, we must pay attention to the context of the situation. Based on the analysis of the context of the situation, we can solve the non-linguistic aspects that can be correlated (Kemal, 2013).

Kampung Meurawoe terkucil dan jarang ada orang lain atau orang asing yang mau datang. Hal ini karena warga kampung tersebut masih sangat tertutup dan tidak segan menggunakan ilmu gaib untuk menyalaki orang lain. Tak ada orang lain di dunia ini yang lebih hebat dibandingkan penduduk kampung Meurawoe yang dapat membuat hidup orang lain merana. Setiap orang asing masuk ke kampung tersebut dengan menampakkan kesombongan, maka ia akan pulang dengan muntah darah. Sejak kedatangan para tentara, kampung tersebut berubah mencekam. Orang-orang yang merasa berkuasa merasa lebih takut terhadap militer pemerintah daripada Tuhan.

techniques in literary research seek to analyze documents in order to find out the contents, meanings, and uses contained in these documents. Content analysis can be said to be the latest study model. content analysis is used when the researcher wants to uncover, understand, and capture the messages of literary works (Endraswara and Jaborihim in Aristya, 2016).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the research conducted, the meaning of the cynicism style contained in the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* by Arafat Nur, namely (1) contextual meaning, (2) conceptual meaning, (3) connotative meaning, (4) collocative meaning, (5) affective meaning, (6) social meaning, (7) thematic meaning. The research results are presented in the form of tables and quotes that have been analyzed.

The story fragment shows that indirectly the character in the story above satirizes the builder whose house itself is very bad. In fact, he was able to build other people's houses. Builder is a phrase that contains a collocative meaning, namely a meaning that contains associations that a word acquires, caused by the meanings of words that tend to appear in its environment.

A builder has the meaning of a person who has the expertise to build a house. The above is commonplace. A builder will build someone else's house splendidly, while his own house goes unnoticed. Likewise with clothes, a builder will pay more attention to the needs of his house than thinking about clothes. Apart from that, the diction is very strange indeed if the builders, even the house itself does not have time to repair it also shows a style of cynicism.

Table 2: Affective Meaning

No	occurrence Number	occurrence	Page
1	26	<i>Pasha Alibasyah mengeluh</i>	47-51
2	35	<i>Saidul melewati rumah Zahra</i>	83-87
3	54	<i>Saidul heran melihat tingkah Ayah dan Sani</i>	190-195
4	59	<i>Para tentara tertawa</i>	223-227
5	65	<i>Saidul memakai celana koyak</i>	318-321
6	67	<i>Belum mau kawin</i>	332-336

The table above is data showing affective meaning in Arafat Nur novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*. Affective meaning reflects one's feelings from the speaker, including attitudes towards the other person, or towards something being discussed. Affective meaning is the meaning that arises because of the response or reaction of a listener or reader to the use of diction or sentences (Wardha, Diah Isti Fauziah; Nurhadi, 2021). A word or sentence is said to have an affective meaning if the word has a sense of value, either positive or negative.

Pasha kept complaining, complaining to me, as if I were a law official who had come to solve his problem. He even forgot to ask about my need to come here which really didn't have any interest. If only he had asked me, I would have turned around and gone home.

Cynic language style is characterized by as if I were a law official which is a phrase that contains an affective meaning, namely a meaning that reflects the speaker's personal feelings. Saidul said he was as if he was a legal official because his friend always used him to solve his friend's problems.

The expression in the quotation above shows the feelings of the speaker who does not like his friend who always makes him a place to solve problems. My character says this because he is always used to solve other people's problems. The word as if what he said meant that he did not want to help solve other people's problems.

Table 3: Social Meaning

No	occurrence Number	occurrence	Page
1	38	<i>Saidul ragu terhadap pencipta perangkap burung</i>	101-105

Some of the words used are identified as a dialect which describes the origin of the speaker, and other features describe the relationship that the speaker and listener have.

Tepat di seberang jalan sana adalah rumah batu besar dan megah milik Pasha Alibasyah, si tuan tanah kaya dan kikir. Lelaki itu tampak sedang duduk di kursi beranda dengan kepala menekur, ditemani istri dan empat anaknya yang hampir dalam keadaan yang sama.

The style of cynicism is marked by rich and miserly. The word rich shows one strengths among people who don't have it. In the story quote above, there are not many rich

people in the village, so the word rich shows social status. Stingy means a stingy person. The title of the landlord is the name for Pasha Alibasyah.

Pasha Alibasyah is a rich man who owns a lot of land. However, people do not like it because it has a miserly nature. The word miserly in the quote above contains a social meaning. The word miserly is a title or nickname that is said by the community towards the character Pasha Alibasyah in the story. The figure is said to be miserly because he has a lot of wealth, but does not want to share it with people in need. Therefore, the word stingy in the quotation above refers to social meaning.

Table 4: Thematic Meaning

No	occurrence Number	occurrence	Page
1	3	<i>Murtala menanyakan Saidul tidak sekolah</i>	11-15
2	25	<i>Pasha Alibasyah sedang duduk di kursi</i>	45-49
3	51	<i>Keluarga Saidul mengadakan pesta</i>	187-192
4	53	<i>Saidul tampak ketakutan</i>	210-215

Some kinds of parts of a sentence can also be used as a subject, object or complement to show excellence. This is done through focus, topic or emotional emphasis. It can be concluded that the thematic meaning is the meaning that is communicated depending on how the speaker or writer arranges the message, in terms of the order of focus and emphasis.

Thematic meaning is what is communicated by the way in which a speaker or writer organizes the message, in terms of ordering, focus, and emphasis (Leech in Swarniti, 2021).

Namun, aku tetap ragu bahwa pencipta pertama perangkap burung ini orang Indonesia. Setahuku, sepanjang usia yang telah kulalui sampai sekarang, orang Indonesia hanya mampu menciptakan karet gelang. Memang karet gelang ini banyak juga manfaatnya. Selain sebagai pengikat

mulut plastik kemasan, juga sangat bagus digunakan untuk menjepret pantat kucing nakal.

The style of cynicism is characterized by Indonesians only being able to create rubber bands. Rubber bands are phrases that contain thematic meanings, that is, the meaning communicated depends on how the speaker or writer arranges the message, in terms of order of focus and emphasis. At that time the technology was not as advanced as it is now. Apart from that, human resources are also a factor in latex processing, only rubber bands are made. The thematic meaning of the cynicism style in the above quotation shows the people's distrust of the government, which always

innovates with technology. As village people, they think that Indonesia is only capable of making small tools or those that can be considered trivial.

B. Discussion

Based on the results of the research above, the meaning of cynicism in the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* by Arafat Nur are contain (1) nine contextual meanings, (2) nine data conceptual meanings, (3) three data connotative meanings, (4) collocative meaning of two data, (5) affective meaning of six data, (6) social meaning of four data, (7) thematic meaning of one data.

Fig. 1: Graph of Total Data on the Meaning of Cynicism

Presentation of the number of findings on the meaning of cynicism in the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* by Arafat Nur. It can be stated that the language style of cynicism is contextual and conceptual which is more commonly found, namely nine findings each. Contextual language style is the expression of meaning based on context or situation. The language style of conceptual meaning cynicism is a style of language that is expressed based on the actual meaning. This happens because the emotional control when speaking is inappropriate so that the language of cynicism is expressed without thinking about the effect or it could be that the disclosure of cynicism with actual (conceptual) meaning is spoken in a planned manner. In a conversation someone satirizes the other person according to the situation experienced. In the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*, the character of the war situation between the two parties and society as a victim changes. A person's character determines the style of language. A war situation will cause mutual distrust to increase. Emotional tends to be unmanageable. Therefore, the people who spoke during the war were dominated by cynicism, contextual and conceptual meanings.

Jannah (2021) conducted research on forms of violence in the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*, the findings presented by the behavior of the characters and the language used. The types and types of language styles used in the novel are not disclosed. Nurmawar (2020) analyzes human rights violations in the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*, findings of ways of conveying human rights violations in the novel. It can be stated that this research is included in studying language, but does not analyze language style.

Based on previous research on the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* by Arafat Nur, it can be explained that this research and previous research both studied language, the findings of the analysis were based on the style of language in the novel, but did not explain the details of the research results. The findings in this study mention what the meanings and use of language styles contained in the novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi* by Arafat Nur. Research data obtained from the paraphrase of the novel to events.

Furthermore, the same study on novels on language style, such as Susilowati (2016) Language Style in Asma Nadia's *Pesantren Impian* Novel, the findings of the research results mention what types of language styles are in the novel studied. Herman, et al (2018) analyzed the Irony Style in Thayeb Loh Angen's Novel *Teuntra Atom* to find types of ironic language styles. Cahyo, et al (2020) analyzed the use of sarcasm in Jason Ranti's Communist Danger Song. In the same study, the smallest part of the research subject was not explained, such as the type of language style. So that the findings conveyed are any style of language so that the results obtained are general. In this study, the studies carried out were derived from the names of figurative languages, the studies that revealed what the meanings and usages were so that this research was not fixated on looking for any style of language.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on research on the meaning of cynicism in Arafat Nur's novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*, seven meanings of cynicism were found, namely contextual meaning, conceptual meaning, connotative meaning, affective meaning, social meaning, and thematic meaning. The purpose of this research is to determine what the cynicism style means in Arafat Nur novel *Bayang Suram Pelangi*. The implication of this research is to facilitate further research that wants to examine the derivatives of cynicism in the novel. This research can be a reference for further research.

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